

Operational Plan for All Academic and Institutional Libraries

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Abstract: This article will help to understand the Operational Plan details related information and it will help people to make their knowledge grow. The Strategic Plan defines the idea and procedure of strategic planning and goes some way to explaining how it first appeared in the workplace in the 1960s before being adopted by library and information services in the 1970s with help from trade organizations and governmental organizations that supported the development of best practices. Will describe ground-breaking work on the subject, define basic planning stages, and list the advantages of strategic planning for libraries. With annotations, it enables us to understand scholarly works as well as read suggestions. The Annual Operational Plan of the Library of any educational institution corresponds to the current year. The strategic and operational objectives will be aimed at reinforcing the weak points and carrying out the necessary improvements to provide quality and excellent service. The Annual Operating Plan Development (AOPD) can carry out the following actions: take into account the strategic plan of the institute; select, analyze, and present proposals for actions for the current year, within the strategic lines; and general and operational objectives of the strategic plan. Institute offers excellent services that meet the needs of research and contribute to the dissemination of scientific production of the institute. People and organization: guarantee the professionalism of all library staff and propose an efficient training plan and permanent professional updating in an optimal working environment. The plan will be monitored by the Strategic Plan Group, which may propose the necessary adjustments.

Keywords: educational institution, library management system, operational objective, strategic plan

1 INTRODUCTION

The Annual Operational Plan of the Library of any educational institution corresponds to the current year. Every educational institution has a strategic plan to develop the institution's system, use it, and make it easy to use in a minimum amount of time. Every institute has its own path or way to reach the goal or vision of developing theme salve.

The actions have followed the same main axes of the Strategic Plan, which are the following:

1. Learning and teaching
2. Axis of Scientific Advancement and Knowledge Transfer
3. Individuals and organizations
4. Quality, continuous improvement, and perspective.
5. Alliances, cooperation, and society

These strategic axes are in line with those of the institute. The strategic and operational objectives will be aimed at reinforcing the weak points and carrying out the necessary improvements to provide quality and excellent service. This plan has been validated by the Institute Board of Directors and approved by the General Library Commission.

1.1 Objectives

1. The authors' goal is to have a direct or indirect impact on society.
2. To know about the strategic plan of any institute that can work as per the system defined here.
3. A general concept will build which is required for every professional.

1.2 Library Collections

The total number of copies is estimated as per the institute's available resources. If the institute has a special research library, then the same kinds of materials are available there. The main types of materials below are kept in the libraries, whether it depends on the user's requirements. Generally, the below-mentioned materials are kept in the library for the users.

- Booklet
- Graphic and cartographic documents
- Drawings
- Photographs
- Posters
- Maps and a series of maps
- Geographic postcards
- Score
- Sound records
- video and

- DVD recordings
- Personal archives

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

A strategic plan, when correctly developed, may make a compelling argument for the library's significance to its sponsoring organization [1]. This book walks readers through a step-by-step approach for preparing for a successful strategic planning process and evaluating the effectiveness of both the process and the final plan. This powerful resource, written by a team of authors with decades of library administration experience between them, empowers academic libraries to develop plans that will provide directional guidance to employees while also showing their ability to accomplish the organization's objectives. shares ideas for including library workers as well as patrons in the planning process.

University libraries are increasingly competing with other academic and support service providers in the university for resources and recognition [2]. As part of their contribution to enabling academic excellence in academic libraries, they are continuing to justify their roles as true academic partners. Addressing the relevance, value, and impact of a university library is a task that the university librarian must continue to articulate and assert. A university's executive management wants to see the link between institutional strategic goals and academic support services, including the library.

The learning and creating diverse and inclusive learning environments. Creating and disseminating original research in library and information science and related fields [3]. At the core of our campus and library is inclusive excellence, which means embracing diversity and inclusion. This plan is not inclusive of everything that we do, there are many activities and services that are not mentioned. In addition to these a number of studies were carried out on library management in the literature [4]-[15].

3 FACTORS TO CONSIDER WHEN DEALING WITH THE LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

3.1 Increase in Funds

Through legal deposit in tangible support, the institute and its various activities can increase funds for the overall development of the institute. As it is known, the library can give the idea to grow the fund, but the institutional library can't generate any funds from the resources, but it is possible to give users more facilities like a reprographic facility, translation facility, etc. It is known that the library is the face of the institute.

3.2 Technical Process

After purchasing the library resources, there are many technical and non-technical steps to be completed by the library professionals. Through this technical process, library resources can be ready for use and searchable.

- Modern monographs
- Old books
- Magazines and newspapers
- Maps and plans
- Drawings, engravings, and photographs.
- Sound recordings
- Manuscripts and other documents
- Electronic publications

3.3 Catalog Growth

The growth of records included in the Integrated Management System Librarian of the particular institute library can be the following:

1. Bibliographic records
2. Records of MARC holdings and
3. Authority records.

3.4 Cultural and Educational Activities

How many cultural and educational activities have been arranged by the institute library? What is its use of it? How many participants participated and how their feedback regarding the cultural program is very important for the institute.

3.5 Personal and Documentary Collections

If anyone donates the reading materials or library materials, they have to keep them as per use, with care, so that in the future, other users can use them and gain knowledge from them.

3.6 Manuscripts

If any original manuscript is available, the institute has to keep it as per the rules with care.

3.7 File & Archive

The academic and institutional archives their books, magazines, newspapers, art, graphs, maps, and digital materials for users, also need to follow up the copyright.

3.8 Interlibrary Loan

Interlibrary loan (abbreviated ILL, and sometimes called interloan, inter-lending, document delivery, document supply, or interlibrary services, abbreviated ILS) is a service whereby a patron of one library can borrow books, DVDs, music, etc. and/or receive photocopies of documents that are owned by another library. The user makes a request with their home library; which, acting as an intermediary, identifies libraries with the desired item, places the request, receives the item, makes it available to the user, as well as arranges for its return. The lending library usually sets a due date and overdue fees for the material borrowed. Although books and journal articles are the most frequently requested items, some libraries will lend audio recordings, video recordings, maps, sheet music, and microforms of all kinds. In some cases, nominal fees accompany the interlibrary loan services.” (“Interlibrary Loan - Wikipedia”)

3.9 Bibliographic Information Service

Bibliographical services are those that deal with the library's collection and access to it, whether in print or online. These services are available online through a website in modern libraries. Many studies have been conducted to investigate the implementation of web 2.0 tools and web-based services provided by libraries. There is a need to research the fundamental library services provided by the web or websites in modern libraries.

In this paper, the author researched top world and Indian libraries, created an inventory of web-based bibliographic services offered by these libraries, and quantitatively analyzed the data.

3.10 Indexing and Abstracting Service

“An abstracting service is a service that provides abstracts of publications, often on a subject or group of related subjects, usually on a subscription basis. An indexing service is a service that assigns descriptors and other kinds of access points to documents. The word indexing service is today mostly used for computer programs but may also cover services providing back-of-the-book indexes, journal indexes, and related kinds of indexes. An indexing and abstracting service is a service that provides shortening or summarizing of documents and assigning of descriptors for referencing documents.” (“Indexing and Abstracting Service - Wikipedia”)

3.11 Methodology and Timetable

The Annual Operating Plan Development Group can carry out the following actions: Take into account the strategic plan of the institute; select, analyze, and present proposals for actions for the current year, within the strategic lines and general and operational objectives of the strategic plan. Prepare and write the first draught of the document. Transfer the proposal to the institute’s Board of Directors for validation. Approve it at the meeting of the Strategic Plan Group. Transfer the proposal to the Vice-Rector for Research and Scientific Policy of the Institute. Transfer the proposal for approval to the General Library Commission and collect the contributions of the members of the said Committee to prepare the final document.

4 ACADEMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL OR INSTITUTE LIBRARY OPERATIONAL PLAN

4.1 Mission

The library is the management unit for the information resources necessary for the academic and institutional community to meet its objectives in terms of teaching, study, learning, and research. Its main purpose is to facilitate access and dissemination of all information resources, both internal and external, to the academic and institutional community, as well as to collaborate in the processes of creation and dissemination of knowledge, contributing to the comprehensive training of the people and leading the scientific and cultural development of society.

4.2 Vision

Consolidate the Academic and institutional library as a key of service at any Academic and institutional library. Workspaces, equipment, and internal and external information will be managed and organized in various formats that are easily accessible to the user. Virtual and face-to-face services will be provided for learning, teaching, and research. This vision is integrated into that of the institute itself, which wants, as stated in its lines of action, to be perceived as an institution. The effective strategic management system that favors the achievement of common objectives through involvement responsible for the entire institutional community:

- a) It has a high-quality undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral training program that is fully aligned with the Space European Higher Education guidelines and tailored to the needs of the social demand.
- b) That pursues the comprehensive training of students and seeks the continuous updating of knowledge.
- c) That it has become a national and international benchmark for its research activity in all areas, for the teaching offer of its postgraduate and doctoral programs, and for the transfer of research results through academic and institutional extension activities, scientific-technical services, the Science Park, the Technology Centers, and other initiatives that

- promote innovative capacity.
- d) It has a motivated, qualified, correctly remunerated, and constantly retrained workforce that has the recognition and support of social agents.
 - e) That it has achieved a high level of quality in the management of resources, the result of which has contributed notably to the stability and financial sufficiency of academics and institutions.
 - f) That it has contracted a high social commitment with the academic and institutional community as well as its regional, national, and international environments, making it a model for the promotion of its cultural and sports promotion programs, social initiatives, and involvement in activities carried out in their field.

Values: The values that define us are the following:

Quality: It offer our users excellent services.

Visibility: It contribute to disseminating the results of the research carried out at the institute.

Accessibility: It facilitate access to our spaces, services, and websites, paying special attention to people with disabilities or functional diversity.

Communication: Through it, establish communication channels, both virtual and face-to-face, between all institutional staff and all users.

Open Access: It adhere to the existing proposals in this framework to share knowledge.

Professionalism: Through it can commit to developing our employees' proas fissional skills most effectively and efficiently possible.

Learning: we promote a higher level of information literacy in our users so that they are self-sufficient.

Evaluation, Monitoring, and Reviews

The Directorate/Board of Directors of the Library and the Strategic Plan Group will propose annual actions to the different sections and libraries, drawing up an Annual Operational Plan which will reflect the execution periods of each project. Every six months or twelve months, the plan will be monitored by the Strategic Plan committee which may propose the necessary adjustments. Annually, the Library Management/Board of Directors will prepare a report on the status of compliance with the objectives, detailing the actions carried out. Cross-cutting working groups will be created to develop the objectives and actions derived from the implementation of the Strategic Plan. These groups will have a coordinator and a secretary and will reflect the agreements of their sessions in the minutes.

Each action has indicators for each improvement project or action that is undertaken, as well as the expected deadlines for its execution. The data and results of these actions will be reflected in the library's Annual Report, which must be approved by the Library Commission of the institute or Academic institutions. Work for the committee or the Library Management will present a Results Report, which will be submitted for the approval of the bodies and commissions/director/board of Govt to those who approved it at the beginning.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Strategic planning in academic libraries has progressed from a management concept to a well-established practice over the last three decades. Higher education planning frameworks and strategy processes have evolved in response to administrative changes and external demands. Convergence of library and computing services is occurring at multiple levels (operational, tactical/developmental, and strategic), as evidenced by the shifting scope of library and information service plans and the development of comprehensive information strategies. The proliferation of strategies is shifting the focus of attention away from the creation and implementation of plans and toward the linking and integration of multiple strategies "web strategy." Academic libraries have generally portrayed their strategic plans as both supporting and influencing the institution's higher-level strategies, but libraries that take advantage of the opportunities offered by creative partnerships to develop joined-up (or joint) plans with related services may see this balance shift and their influence increase." Strategic planning has served us well in the past, and it will continue to help us create a better future if it is continue to adapt and refine our processes and procedures.

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